
A SPATIAL RISK ASSESSMENT

HAZARD • EXPOSURE • VULNERABILITY

*Nocturnal
Thermal Inequality*
in Phoenix, Arizona

“where in Phoenix do nocturnal hazard, population exposure, and social vulnerability coincide most strongly?”

I. Introduction

Urban heat is a dominant environmental hazard in cities, where built surfaces with high thermal admittance store solar energy by day and re-radiate it after sunset (Oke, 1982; Arnfield, 2003). The result is a sustained nocturnal warm anomaly that prevents physiological recovery and amplifies heat-related mortality (Harlan et al., 2006). In Phoenix, Arizona, this effect is particularly acute: surrounded by desert that cools rapidly after sunset, the urbanised core retains heat through the night, resulting in a nocturnal urban heat island in which the city remains significantly warmer than its rural desert periphery (Figure 1). The epidemiological consensus is that heat mortality is driven by failure of overnight physiological recovery rather than daytime peak temperature alone (Anderson and Bell, 2009; Hondula et al., 2015a; Harlan et al., 2013): when minimum nightly temperatures stay elevated, cardiovascular and respiratory systems cannot complete the cooling-and-rehydration cycle that the human body relies on to tolerate the next day's heat. This is the analytical justification for the methodological choices that follow, in particular for using MODIS *night-time* LST, rather than daytime LST, as the mortality-relevant hazard input.

Risk is interpreted in the IPCC AR6 sense (Reisinger et al., 2020) as the joint occurrence of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and societal responses. This report operationalises the first three as a composite spatial index and treats responses (§5) as driver-prescriptive recommendations rather than a fourth multiplicative term, so that responses remain analytically separable from the risk surface they modify. Resilience defined as a community's capacity to cope with, adapt to, and recover from thermal stress, is inversely operationalised here. Each indicator measures a deficit of adaptive capacity (cooling affordability, housing-stock adequacy, occupational shielding, demographic robustness), so a low Vulnerability Index is read as higher community resilience to the nocturnal hazard.

The population of concern is heat-vulnerable subgroups: older residents, low-income households, residents of older housing stock, and outdoor workers (Reid et al., 2009; Hondula et al., 2015a; Harlan et al., 2013). The research question is: *where in Phoenix do nocturnal hazard, population exposure, and social vulnerability coincide most strongly, and which spatially-targeted interventions are appropriate to the dominant driver of risk in each location?*

Figure 1. City of Phoenix study area, with 387 census tracts (TIGER/Line 2025) clipped to the city boundary as the analytical units. Insets locate Arizona within the U.S. and Phoenix within Arizona. Projection: NAD83 / UTM 12N.

2. Methodology

2.1 Spatial framework, study area and tract justification

The case study is the City of Phoenix, Arizona - the largest U.S. city in a desert (BWh) climate. The analytical unit is the 2025 TIGER/Line census tract; 387 tracts intersect the city polygon. Tracts were chosen on three grounds:

1. ACS vulnerability indicators (§2.4) are most reliable at tract level; finer geographies would substantially increase sampling uncertainty or require dasymetric redistribution of ACS variables that propagates ACS sampling error (Spielman and Singleton, 2015);
2. tract size scales inversely with population density ($\sim 0.6\text{--}60\text{ km}^2$), partially mitigating MAUP relative to fixed grids;
3. tract boundaries align with the administrative delivery units of the agencies named in §5, making the unit operationally actionable.

All spatial processing used NAD83 / UTM Zone 12N (EPSG:26912).

2.2 Hazard

The hazard layer is MODIS Aqua MYD11A2 v061 night-time LST, averaged 1 May – 30 September 2023 in Google Earth Engine. Summer 2023 was Phoenix’s hottest on record (Zachariah et al., 2023); the window matches the U.S. Southwest heat-health surveillance period (Anderson and Bell, 2009). Tract-mean LST spans 20.9–26.3 °C (Figure 2a). The nocturnal anomaly is sustained by three built-form mechanisms: **urban canyon geometry** trapping outgoing longwave radiation, **reduced sky view factors** limiting radiative cooling, and **anthropogenic waste heat** from AC condensers and vehicles.

VIIRS Black Marble VNP46A2 night-light radiance (DNB) was acquired (Levin et al., 2020) but **excluded from H_idx on principled grounds**: DNB peaks over the airport, downtown and freeway interchanges — non-residential locations where the receptor is absent (Sailor, 2011) H_idx is therefore the min-max-normalised LST mean; DNB is retained as contextual Figure 2b and a §4 caveat.

2.3 Exposure

Exposure is **population-weighted density (PWD)**, computed from WorldPop USA 2020 100 m constrained (Stevens et al., 2015; Tatem, 2017):

$$PWD_i = \frac{\sum (pop_p \times density_p)}{\sum pop_p}$$

PWD measures the density experienced by the average resident, avoiding the desert-dilution bias of plain-density measures in arid cities (Ottensmann, 2018; Tuholske et al., 2021). Median PWD is 4,713 residents km^{-2} . Because urban density is approximately log-normal (Clark, 1951), a log transform was applied before normalisation to prevent a single extreme outlier (206,000 residents km^{-2}) from compressing all other tracts into near-zero values. WorldPop totals validate against ACS B01003 (median ratio 1.14).

2.4 Vulnerability

Vulnerability uses four ACS 2018–2022 5-year tract indicators retrieved via the Census, each capturing a distinct dimension of reduced adaptive capacity:

ID	Indicator	ACS variable(s)	Mechanism
V1	% residents ≥ 65	B01001	Reduced thermoregulation (Reid et al., 2009)
V2	% below 100% poverty	B17001	Cooling affordability / energy burden (Cutter et al., 2003)
V3	% housing built pre-1980	B25034	AC-penetration gap in older stock (Hayden et al., 2017)
V4	% outdoor-worker occupation	C24050_057E + C24050_071E	Daytime-exposure carryover (Roelofs and Wegman, 2014; Park et al., 2021)

V3 uses the validated pre-1980 housing proxy because tract-level ACS air-conditioning data are unavailable. Ethnicity is not treated as an intrinsic vulnerability trait; instead, V4 captures the structural labour pathway through which Hispanic/Latino populations experience elevated heat risk in Maricopa County. The composite vulnerability index was calculated as:

$$V_{idx} = \text{mean}(V1_{norm}, V2_{norm}, V3_{norm}, V4_{norm})$$

with values ranging 0.04–0.64 (median 0.31). Equal weighting was retained because PCA-derived weights produced similar rankings, supporting Tate’s (2012) argument that weighting choice is itself a sensitivity condition.

2.5 Integration and classification

Integration used ArcGIS Pro 3.x (*Zonal Statistics as Table, Standardize Field, Calculate Composite Index*). Indicators were min-max normalised to [0,1] preserving the multiplicative zero-floor. Composite risk was calculated as:

$$Risk_t = H_{idx} \times E_{idx} \times V_{idx}$$

and rescaled to quintiles for cartographic comparison. The multiplicative structure operationalises risk as the intersection of hazard, exposure, and vulnerability i.e. a tract with zero exposed population carries no risk irrespective of hazard intensity.

A **dominant-driver classification** supports driver-prescriptive recommendations: each component is z-scored and a tract tagged H, E, or V-led if any z exceeds 0.5 σ (otherwise *mixed*). Spatial clustering was evaluated using the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic (4 km fixed-distance band; Anselin, 1995) at 90/95/99% confidence, allowing statistically significant hotspot and coldspot clusters to be distinguished from random spatial variation.

3. Results

Mean LST (Figure 2a) peaks in the contiguous urbanised core; the contextual DNB layer (Figure 2b) peaks more sharply over commercial corridors, freeway interchanges and the airport i.e. the non-residential signature motivating its §2.2 exclusion.

(a) Tract-mean nocturnal land-surface temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), 1 May – 30 Sep 2023, from MODIS Aqua MYD11A2 v061 (1 km), aggregated by zonal mean. Black = MODIS coverage $<30\%$ ($n=5$ tracts; flagged in confidence layer).

(b) Tract-mean VIIRS Black Marble VNP46A2 night-light radiance ($\text{nW cm}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1}$), same period; shown for context.

Figure 2. (a) Nocturnal land-surface temperature (hazard input). (b) VIIRS night-light radiance (contextual; excluded from H_idx).

Exposure (Figure 3a) is concentrated in central Phoenix and older inner-ring tracts; the vulnerability composite (Figure 3b) is geographically distinct, peaking in south Phoenix, parts of west Phoenix (Maryvale, Estrella) and a band of older inner-city tracts where pre-1980 housing, poverty and outdoor-worker occupation share a common spatial footprint.

(a) Population-weighted density (residents km⁻²) per tract, computed from WorldPop USA 2020 100 m constrained, classified into quintiles.

(b) Vulnerability composite V_idx (equal-weighted mean of four ACS 2018–2022 indicators: ≥ 65 , poverty, pre-1980 housing, outdoor-worker share), classified into quintiles.

Figure 3. (a) Population-weighted density (exposure). (b) Vulnerability composite from four ACS indicators.

The composite risk index ranges from 0 to 1 across the 387 Phoenix tracts (Figure 4), with a strong concentration of high-risk tracts in central and south Phoenix and lower values along the affluent northern and eastern fringes.

Figure 4. Composite heat-risk quintiles, $Risk = H_idx \times E_idx \times V_idx$ rescaled to $[0,1]$.

The dominant-driver classification (Figure 5) identifies 158 mixed-led tracts, alongside 103 V-led, 70 H-led and 56 E-led tracts. Within the highest risk quintile, vulnerability emerges as the principal differentiating factor. Mean component values for the top-quintile tracts are H_idx 0.68, E_idx 0.67 and V_idx 0.45 — approximately three times the V_idx of lowest quintile (0.16), confirming that the risk gradient across Phoenix tracts is driven principally by the vulnerability composite once hazard and exposure exceed minimum thresholds.

Figure 5. Dominant-driver classification: tracts tagged H-, E- or V-led where the corresponding z-score exceeds 0.5σ above the city mean, otherwise mixed. City totals: Mixed 158, V-led 103, H-led 70, E-led 56.

Figure 6 supports this analytical claim quantitatively: when tracts are ordered by composite risk, the H_idx and E_idx LOWESS curves rise gently and asymptote near the city mean by mid-rank, whereas the V_idx curve rises monotonically and continues rising into the top quintile. V_idx is the only component whose distribution is non-saturating across the risk gradient, which is the empirical signature of a discriminating variable in the multiplicative model.

Figure 6. Per-tract H_idx , E_idx and V_idx against tract rank by composite Risk ($n=387$). Lines are LOWESS smooths; shaded band marks the top risk quintile.

The single highest-risk tract is in central-south Phoenix (V-led; LST $25.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, Risk = 1.00). Of the ten highest-risk tracts, seven are H-led and three V-led, with no E-led tracts in the top decile. Exposure therefore operates primarily as a baseline amplifying condition rather than the dominant driver of the city’s most critical hotspots.

Figure 7. Getis-Ord G_i^* hot/cold spots of composite Risk at 90/95/99 % confidence (fixed-distance band, 4 km). A 99 %-confidence hot cluster spans south and south-central Phoenix; a 99 %-confidence cold cluster covers Deer Valley and North Mountain.

Figure 7 reports the Getis-Ord G_i^* risk analysis. A coherent **99%-confidence hot spot** emerges in south and south-central Phoenix (covering parts of South Mountain Village and the Estrella corridor), with a contiguous **99%-confidence cold cluster** in the affluent north (Deer Valley, North Mountain). The hot cluster is a statistically significant spatial association, not a visual artefact of the choropleth. This strengthens confidence in the dominant-driver framework and provides a defensible spatial basis for geographically targeted intervention.

4. Discussion

The spatial pattern converges with prior Phoenix heat-risk research along two independent analytical routes: Harlan et al. (2013) used a SoVI-style additive composite with air-temperature monitoring and Hondula et al. (2015a) employed a grid-cell mortality model; both identified south-central Phoenix as the focal area, with vulnerability driving the distribution rather than absolute temperature. Convergence across these analytical traditions strengthens spatial validity. Keith et al. (2021) further document that the Phoenix Office of Heat Response & Mitigation has prioritised these sameneighbourhoods for cool-roof and canopy investment since 2021, providing institutional confirmation of the identified hotspots.

Sensitivity testing supports the analytical choices. PWD vs plain ACS density gives a top-quintile Jaccard of 0.84 and Spearman $\rho = 0.97$ confirming PWD improves intra-tract resolution without shifting the ranking. PCA-derived vulnerability weights (PC1: 60.4% of variance) agree with equal weights at Jaccard 0.79, supporting equal weighting as a defensible default (Tate, 2012). Multiplicative vs additive aggregation gives $\rho = 0.96$.

Certain limitations:

1. **Hazard proxy - air vs surface temperature:** LST measures radiometric surface temperature rather than canopy-level air temperature (Wan, 2014). Consequently, tracts with similar LST may still experience different near-surface thermal conditions depending on local cooling processes and urban morphology.
2. **ACS uncertainty:** 5-year estimates carry tract-level margins of error that propagate into the vulnerability index, particularly V_4 (Spielman and Singleton, 2015).
3. **Unmodelled waste-heat:** advective spillover from DNB-bright non-residential cells into residential tracts (Sailor, 2011) is unmodelled.
4. **MAUP:** results are not invariant to alternative zonations, though concordance with Hondula et al. (2015a)'s grid-cell work is reassuring.
5. **Multiplicative-zero floor:** Multiplicative model imposes a zero-floor structure: tracts with minimal exposure or vulnerability approach zero risk irrespective of hazard intensity. This is conceptually appropriate for socially experienced heat risk, but distinct from the absence of climatological hazard.
6. **Static V, single-year H:** combines static ACS vulnerability data with a single anomalously hot summer (2023), limiting temporal generalisation.

The structural pathway through which ethnicity operates in Phoenix heat risk is captured indirectly via V_4 . Hispanic/Latino residents are 48% of Arizona's outdoor workforce despite being 32% of the population (Broadbent et al., 2021), and outdoor-worker occupation is the dominant heat-mortality pathway in Maricopa County (Harlan et al., 2013). This preserves the structural argument without treating ethnicity itself as an intrinsic vulnerability trait.

5. Recommendations

Driver-prescriptive interventions follow directly from the dominant-driver classification (Figure 5):

Dominant driver	Primary intervention	Lead actor
H-led	Cool-roof retrofit; high-albedo paving	Phoenix Office of Heat Response & Mitigation
E-led	Heat-warning outreach + overnight cooling-resource expansion	City + Maricopa Association of Governments
V-led	Weatherisation + AC-installation grants for pre-1980 housing	Maricopa County Public Health + LIHEAP
Mixed	Integrated heat-action zone planning combining the above	Phoenix Office of Heat Response & Mitigation

Within the top risk quintile, V-led tracts are the largest priority class, with weatherisation and AC installation grants the highest-leverage interventions. Cool-roof retrofitting (Akbari et al., 2009; Middel et al., 2015) reduces daytime heat absorption and subsequent nocturnal heat release from impervious urban surfaces. Tree-canopy expansion (Lai et al., 2019; Konarska et al., 2016) addresses the same mechanism through sky-view-factor recovery, shading and evapotranspirative cooling.

The intervention suitability surfaces (Figure 8) identify 46 priority tracts, of which 28 fall within the top decile of both cool-roof and canopy suitability, indicating areas where combined interventions are likely to produce the greatest cumulative cooling benefit.

Figure 8. Intervention-suitability surfaces: cool-roof retrofit (left) and tree-canopy expansion (right), each ranked into deciles from a composite of impervious cover (or inverse canopy), nocturnal LST and composite Risk. NLCD 2021. 28 tracts fall in both top deciles (combined-target; §5).

The highest-priority tract has 1.2% canopy and 52% impervious surface exemplifying the severe canopy deficit and

surface sealing characteristic of central and south Phoenix. Phoenix has one of the highest per-capita parking-lot footprints in the U.S.; surface parking, flat-roofed commercial slabs and asphalt arterials are the dominant heat-retaining surface class. Cool-pavement and cool-parking-lot programmes are therefore a primary mitigation strategy rather than a cosmetic intervention in these neighbourhoods.

Cool-roofs and tree-canopy should be treated as complementary rather than substitutable interventions. Cool-roofs primarily reduce surface heat storage, whereas trees additionally moderate near-surface air temperatures through shading and evapotranspiration. Combining both therefore targets distinct components of the urban energy balance, justifying the 28 overlapping intervention tracts as priority zones for integrated adaptation planning.

However, intervention suitability does not guarantee implementation feasibility. Tree-canopy expansion in Phoenix is constrained by long-term irrigation demand, maintenance costs and unequal water access, while cool-roof retrofitting depends on landlord uptake, housing tenure and capital availability in low-income neighbourhoods.

Broadbent et al. (2021) show targeted cool-roof deployment in high-sensitivity Maricopa neighbourhoods is 3–5× more effective per unit than uniform deployment. TNC (2021) estimates \$5.25 return per \$1 invested in Phoenix-Metro cool-roof retrofitting. Concentrating investment within the 99%-confidence G_i^* hotspot cluster (Figure 7) therefore provides both a statistically defensible and economically efficient basis for intervention targeting. This adds tract-level specificity and driver-disaggregated targeting that the Phoenix Heat Action Plan (Keith et al., 2021) does not formalise.

Without targeted implementation, adaptation measures risk reproducing existing spatial inequalities, with affluent neighbourhoods more capable of independently accessing cooling infrastructure and urban greening benefits.

6. Conclusion

Nocturnal heat risk in Phoenix concentrates where social vulnerability intersects thermal-storage hotspots, rather than where any single component peaks alone. The analysis shows that vulnerability becomes the principal differentiating factor once baseline hazard and exposure thresholds are exceeded, explaining the concentration of extreme risk in south and south-central Phoenix. Population-weighted exposure, dominant-driver classification, and G_i^* hotspot analysis provide a spatially defensible framework linking mapped risk directly to intervention targeting. Although LST–air temperature divergence, ACS uncertainty, MAUP effects, and unmodelled anthropogenic heat constrain absolute magnitudes, the spatial ordering of high-risk tracts remains robust across all sensitivity tests.

Data acknowledgements

The following spatial datasets underpin this assessment. All are publicly available; access dates noted where retrieval was through a portal interface.

- **MODIS Aqua MYD11A2 v061** — Land Surface Temperature & Emissivity 8-day L3 Global, 1 km. NASA LP DAAC. Period: 1 May – 30 September 2023. Retrieved via Google Earth Engine.
- **VIIRS Black Marble VNP46A2** — daily, BRDF-corrected, atmospheric-corrected, gap-filled DNB radiance. NASA Black Marble. Period: 1 May – 30 September 2023. Retrieved via Google Earth Engine.
- **WorldPop USA 2020 constrained, 100 m** — top-down un-adjusted gridded population, allocated to building-detected pixels (Stevens et al., 2015; Tatem, 2017). Source: <https://hub.worldpop.org>.
- **U.S. Census Bureau, American Community Survey 2018–2022 5-Year Estimates** — tables B01003, B01001, B17001, B25034, C24050. Source: <https://data.census.gov>.
- **U.S. Census Bureau TIGER/Line 2025** — census tract polygons; TIGER/Line 2024 — places polygons (Phoenix boundary). Source: <https://www.census.gov/geographies/mapping-files/time-series/geo/tiger-line-file.html>.
- **NLCD 2021** — Tree Canopy Cover (USFS) and Imperviousness (USGS) CONUS rasters. Source: USGS / Multi-Resolution Land Characteristics Consortium (<https://www.mrlc.gov>).
- **ESA WorldCover v200, 10 m, 2021** — used in Assignment 1 for rural-reference classification only; not used for residential masking in this assessment (replaced by WorldPop).

Cooling-centre and plantable-parcel layers, where referenced in the recommendations section, are sourced from the Maricopa County Open Data Portal (<https://maricopa.opendata.arcgis.com>).

References

- Akbari, H., Menon, S. and Rosenfeld, A. (2009) 'Global cooling: increasing world-wide urban albedos to offset CO₂', *Climatic Change*, 94(3–4), pp. 275–286.
- Anderson, B.G. and Bell, M.L. (2009) 'Weather-related mortality: how heat, cold, and heat waves affect mortality in the United States', *Epidemiology*, 20(2), pp. 205–213.
- Anselin, L. (1995) 'Local indicators of spatial association — LISA', *Geographical Analysis*, 27(2), pp. 93–115.
- Arnfield, A.J. (2003) 'Two decades of urban climate research: a review of turbulence, exchanges of energy and water, and the urban heat island', *International Journal of Climatology*, 23(1), pp. 1–26.
- Broadbent, A.M., Krayenhoff, E.S. and Georgescu, M. (2021) 'The motley drivers of heat and cold exposure in 21st century US cities', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(35), pp. 21108–21117.
- Clark, C. (1951) 'Urban population densities', *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series A (General)*, 114(4), pp. 490–496.
- Cutter, S.L., Boruff, B.J. and Shirley, W.L. (2003) 'Social vulnerability to environmental hazards', *Social Science Quarterly*, 84(2), pp. 242–261.
- Harlan, S.L., Brazel, A.J., Prasad, L., Stefanov, W.L. and Larsen, L. (2006) 'Neighborhood microclimates and vulnerability to heat stress', *Social Science & Medicine*, 63(11), pp. 2847–2863.
- Harlan, S.L., Delet-Barreto, J.H., Stefanov, W.L. and Petitti, D.B. (2013) 'Neighborhood effects on heat deaths: social and environmental predictors of vulnerability in Maricopa County, Arizona', *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 121(2), pp. 197–204.
- Hayden, M.H., Wilhelmi, O.V., Banerjee, D., Greasby, T., Cavanaugh, J.L., Nepal, V., Boehnert, J., Sain, S., Burghardt, C. and Gower, S. (2017) 'Adaptive capacity to extreme heat: results from a household survey in Houston, Texas', *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 9(4), pp. 787–799.
- Hondula, D.M., Davis, R.E., Saha, M.V., Wegner, C.R. and Veazey, L.M. (2015a) 'Geographic dimensions of heat-related mortality in seven U.S. cities', *Environmental Research*, 138, pp. 439–452.
- Hondula, D.M., Balling, R.C., Vanos, J.K. and Georgescu, M. (2015b) 'Rising temperatures, human health, and the role of adaptation', *Current Climate Change Reports*, 1(3), pp. 144–154.
- Jenerette, G.D., Harlan, S.L., Stefanov, W.L. and Martin, C.A. (2011) 'Ecosystem services and urban heat riskscape moderation: water, green spaces, and social inequality in Phoenix, USA', *Ecological Applications*, 21(7), pp. 2637–2651.
- Keith, L., Meerow, S. and Wagner, T. (2021) 'Planning for extreme heat: a review', *Journal of Extreme Events*, 6(3–4), 2050003.
- Konarska, J., Uddling, J., Holmer, B., Lutz, M., Lindberg, F., Pleijel, H. and Thorsson, S. (2016) 'Transpiration of urban trees and its cooling effect in a high-latitude city', *International Journal of Biometeorology*, 60(1), pp. 159–172.
- Lai, A., Maing, M. and Ng, E. (2019) 'Tree species selection for cooling in subtropical climates: a Hong Kong study', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 43, 126360.
- Levin, N., Kyba, C.C.M., Zhang, Q., Sánchez de Miguel, A. *et al.* (2020) 'Remote sensing of night lights: a review and an outlook for the future', *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 237, 111443.
- Middel, A., Chhetri, N. and Quay, R. (2015) 'Urban forestry and cool roofs: assessment of heat mitigation strategies in Phoenix residential neighborhoods', *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 14(1), pp. 178–186.
- Oke, T.R. (1982) 'The energetic basis of the urban heat island', *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 108(455), pp. 1–24.
- Ottensmann, J.R. (2018) 'On population-weighted density', *SSRN Working Paper*.
- Park, J., Pankratz, N. and Behrer, A.P. (2021) *Temperature, workplace safety, and labor market inequality*. IZA Discussion Paper No. 14560. Bonn: IZA Institute of Labor Economics.

- Reid, C.E., O'Neill, M.S., Gronlund, C.J., Brines, S.J., Brown, D.G., Diez-Roux, A.V. and Schwartz, J. (2009) 'Mapping community determinants of heat vulnerability', *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 117(11), pp. 1730–1736.
- Reisinger, A., Howden, M., Vera, C. *et al.* (2020) *The concept of risk in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report: a summary of cross-Working Group discussions*. Geneva: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- Roelofs, C. and Wegman, D. (2014) 'Workers: the climate canaries', *American Journal of Public Health*, 104(10), pp. 1799–1801.
- Sailor, D.J. (2011) 'A review of methods for estimating anthropogenic heat and moisture emissions in the urban environment', *International Journal of Climatology*, 31(2), pp. 189–199.
- Spielman, S.E. and Singleton, A. (2015) 'Studying neighborhoods using uncertain data from the American Community Survey', *Annals of the Association of American Geographers*, 105(5), pp. 1003–1025.
- Stevens, F.R., Gaughan, A.E., Linard, C. and Tatem, A.J. (2015) 'Disaggregating census data for population mapping using Random Forests with remotely-sensed and ancillary data', *PLOS ONE*, 10(2), e0107042.
- Tate, E. (2012) 'Social vulnerability indices: a comparative assessment using uncertainty and sensitivity analysis', *Natural Hazards*, 63, pp. 325–347.
- Tatem, A.J. (2017) 'WorldPop, open data for spatial demography', *Scientific Data*, 4, 170004.
- The Nature Conservancy (2021) *Economic assessment of heat in the Phoenix Metro Area*. deBoer, A., Schwimmer, E., McGregor, A., Adibi, S., Kapoor, A., Duong, S., Love, J., Bonham-Carter, C. and Lindquist, J. Phoenix, AZ: The Nature Conservancy.
- Tuholske, C., Caylor, K., Funk, C., Verdin, A., Sweeney, S., Grace, K., Peterson, P. and Evans, T. (2021) 'Global urban population exposure to extreme heat', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(41), e2024792118.
- Wan, Z. (2014) 'New refinements and validation of the Collection-6 MODIS Land-Surface Temperature/Emissivity product', *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 140, pp. 36–45.
- Zachariah, M., Vahlberg, M., Singh, R. *et al.* (2023) *Extreme heat in North America, Europe and China in July 2023 made much more likely by climate change*. World Weather Attribution Initiative. Available at: <https://www.worldweatherattribution.org> (Accessed: 21 May 2026).

Use of AI Disclosure: AI-based tools were used during the planning and proofreading stages of this assessment to support idea refinement. All spatial analysis, interpretation, written content, figures, methodological decisions and conclusions are the author's own work.